

Tracing Genesis of the Lasting Conflict and the Extent of the Legitimacy of Israel According To The Theory of Recognition and Jews' Original Homeland

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 05,2026</p> <p>Accepted: April 06,2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Lasting Conflict, Colonial States, Zionist Movement, International Legitimacy, Theory Of Recognition, International Law, Arab Israeli Conflict</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19442731</p>	<p><i>The study aimed at tracing and analyzing the reasons that stood behind the lasting conflict in the region as well as to refutation legitimacy of Israel according to the theory of recognition in shedding light on the original homeland of the Jews. It discussed the reasons that caused the conflict in the region continued for more than hundred years, as well as the denial of the allegations on which Israel relied in its establishment with the support of the Zionist movement and the colonial states, the extent of Israeli legitimacy in light of the non-commitment of the sponsoring countries to establish the State of Palestine, in addition to clarifying the original home of Jews, little known about it in this world. The study reached a point that the colonial states were behind establishment of Israel in the region to be used as a functional state for the perpetuation of colonialism in the region, despite the existence of a Jewish homeland that had been previously announced in Birobidzhan, before the declaration of the Jewish state in Palestine that made Israel a rebellious state even against some colonial states that created it, as well as the legitimacy and international law.</i></p>

Introduction

West Asia occupies a significant position in the international relations. This region comprises the Asian countries, south of the former Soviet Union and west of Pakistan. It includes most of the Arab countries with a population of about (453) million people, covering a geographic area as the size of the United States (ar.wikipedia.org,2021). Sometimes the term Middle East is also used for this area. This area has been transformed into a dangerous cockpit of international politics since the World War II, because the people of almost of all the ideologies have been making efforts to win over the people of this area to their side. This keen interest in the region has been due to its unique geographical position. The strategic significance of the region lies in the fact that it forms the land bridge between three continents, Europe, Asia and Africa and thus gives to the occupant not only great land advantage, but also a favorable position to counter sea-power. It is also the center of international communication, because some of the shortest sea and air routes between the continents lie through the region. The two most significant water ways of the world viz., the straits connecting the Black Sea with the Mediterranean and Suez connecting the Red Sea with the Mediterranean are also located in this region. Therefore the significance of the region cannot be over emphasized. Apart from the geographical and strategic significance of the region its uniqueness consists in the fact that it is the Centre of Islamic culture. Moreover, it encompasses the holy places of Jews, Christians and Muslims alike (Lenczowski, 1962: pp. 23-24).

But probably the most significant factors which have contributed to the world-wide significance of this region are, the air-communication links and the presence of large deposits of oil reserves. The swift airways and the discovery of oil in the region at the beginning of the last century led to a new competition among the industrial states, USA, UK, USSR and France for the control of these resources (Gupta, 1965: p. 205).

Apart from the natural resources another feature of West Asian Politics is the Arab-Israeli conflict. The deliberate induction of the Jewish problem into West Asian Politics was a part of imperialist strategy (Banerji, 1960: p.3).

Thus, the geographical and physical features of the region provide a clue character of West Asian conflicts. This region must be understood in the context of Arab nationalism, Western imperialism, and Zionism which are the three main factors that have conditioned West Asian politics since the end of World War I. The intensification of the cold war in the post-World War II era added new problems. In recent years most of the countries of the world, in order to protect their interests have paid attention to the region. The fear of communist penetration and the Western response in forming military alliances have made the region problem a part of international politics, especially centered on them two superpowers, the USA and the USSR.

2. The General Framework of the Study:

2.1. Significance of Study:

It is important to highlight and know some of the hidden facts related to the region as well. The significance of the study lies in the fact that it is complementary to many studies that addressed and examined the historical and religious allegations of Zionist extremist thought; what the aggressive Zionist movement seeks, whether at the intellectual level or in practice, that amounts to terrorizing the organized and programmed approach against the region and its people.

One of the scientific significance of this study is benefits scholars, researchers, interested persons and political analysts in the field of Zionist political thought and Western colonialism, in providing of information and facts that clarify the nature and reality of what has been happening in the region for more than a century. While the practical significance of this study lies in the importance and necessity of informing the politicians of the concerned countries about the conflict in the region and knowing the dimensions of this eternal conflict and how to deal with it at the level of theory and practice in the coming years.

2.2. Problem of Study:

It is important to know the reasons behind the perpetuation of the conflict in the region for more than a century. As well as the reason for the conspiracy of the colonial countries against this region to create a state characterized by racism and hatred for the countries and people of the region; that is trying, with the support of the colonial countries, to control this entire region, which made the people of the region under a permanent siege, while Israel, despite its defiance of international law due to its systematic practices, is free to move in all directions without deterrence. Therefore, this study wanted to recall that Israel never was a part of this region, but rather its beginnings were in a region other than Palestine, so it must have shed light on it and reminded the world of it again.

2.3. Hypothesis of Study:

The study starts from the hypothesis that; there is a correlative relationship between the planning of Western colonial countries by planting a colonial entity embodied in Israel, that practices its illegal and immoral policies in defiance of international legitimacy with the support of colonial countries keen to perpetuate the conflict in the region that made Israel a state outside international law to serve their interests for centuries to come.

2.4. Questions of Study:

The study raises a number of questions attempt to represent what is the motive for the colonial countries' adoption of the idea of establishing Israel in the region?, what are the claims adopted by the Zionist movement in persuading the Jews of the world to immigrate to Palestine despite the fact that they have a homeland in Birobidzhan?, What are the means exercised by Israel as a functional state in achieving the dream of the Zionist movement in the region?, What is required of the regional countries to do in order to counter the Zionist imperialist colonial dream?.

2.5. Objectives of Study:

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives: Being acquainted with the truth about the interest of the colonial countries and their supporting the idea of planting Israel in the region; refuting the allegations and lies adopted by the Zionist movement to attract the attention of the Jews of the world to Palestine; exposing the Israeli practices against the region as a functional state that works for the benefit of the colonial states. Finally, clarifying what the countries of the region, especially the Arab countries, should do to stop this colonial Zionist conspiracy.

2.6. Methodology of Study:

Reviewing the objectives of study, it follows the historical, descriptive, analytical and legal methods. The study used these methods for the purposes of answering the study questions and testing the hypothesis as well.

3. Theoretical / Historical Background of Study:

The substance of the Arab-Israeli conflict may lie in the Palestine question. At present Israel occupies more than what formerly undivided Palestine under the British mandate was secured from the League of Nations after World War I. Palestine has been holding a significant position in the political and cultural history of the region for a number of centuries. Palestine has been known as the land of peace and prophets for many centuries. As an ancient land, it had been holy to the three great religions, Judaism, Christianity and Islam (The Afro-Asian Journalist, 1970: p.6). Palestine lies at the crossroads of major imperial systems based at various times. The last imperial power to rule Palestine was Britain which was in effect a power totally alien to this part of the world. Palestine was inhabited, at the dawn of history, by Canaanites who emigrated from the Arabian Peninsula. Lying on the cross-roads of the region, Palestine was successively invaded by different peoples, Philistines, Hebrews, Greeks, Persians, Romans, Crusaders and Turks (Berindranath; 1969, p.13).

The significance of the permanent conflict in the region revolves around who owns the land, the Jews or the Arabs. According to some scholars, among them Professor Arnold Toynbee, "When one considers the question of whether Palestine belongs to the Jews or to the Arabs, it cannot be said that after a lapse of 800 years it (Palestine) is the land of the Jews alone. Otherwise, the United States of America should now belong to the Red Indians and the situation in England and in many other countries of the world should be no different.

The Jews have no exclusive rights in Palestine except their right to personal property. They do not have right to establish a state. It is most unfortunate that a state is established on a religious basis". (Dewan,1966: p.6. p.18).

3.1. *Are Arabs and Jews really cousins?*

Before Abraham died, according to the Bible, the Lord appeared to him and said, "I give unto thee, and to thy seed after thee, the land wherein thou art a stranger, all the land of Canaan, for an everlasting possession" (Genesis 17:18). Abraham had two sons. One was Isaac, to whom the Jews trace their descent. According to the Bible, God confirmed his "Everlasting Covenant" with Isaac, and through Isaac's son Jacob, with every succeeding generation of Jews (Donovan, 1967, p.6). Abraham's other son was Ishmael, from whom the Arabs claim their descent. According to the Qur'an, the holy book of Islam, God promise Ishmael that he and his seed would prevail. Thus, the Holy writs seem to promise conflict. The Arabs and the Jews thus belong to the same Semitic Race and could legitimately be called 'cousins' and the children of Abraham (Berindranath, 1969: p.14).

The fact was that Jews and Arabs had lived together in peace and harmony for centuries in Palestine as also elsewhere in the Arab World. The Jews fleeing from Europe found asylum, shelter and tolerance in the Arab and Muslim countries. Arabs and Jews had much in common in beliefs and traditions. Thus the British policy drove a wedge between the two "cousins" in Palestine. The Palestine Arabs had no quarrel with the local Jews who already inhabited the common homeland of Palestine. They were opposed to a Zionist state being artificially created in Palestine at the expense of the indigenous Arab people.

4. **Tracing and Analysis of the Lasting Conflict in the Region:**

There is little doubt that Arab nationalism and Zionism remained major adversaries on the west Asian scene. Jews never lost the hope of returning to the claimed Promised Land. In the last half of the 19th Century a movement for creating an independent Jewish State started. This movement is known as Zionism. The founder of the World Zionist Organization was Theodore Hertzl, a native of Budapest who was convinced that in a world of recurrent anti-Semitic pogroms, only the establishment of a Jewish homeland could safe-guard the rights of the Jewish people. Hertzl and the Zionists based their case primarily on the ancient Hebraic Biblical claim to the Promised Land from which Jews had been driven into the Diaspora. Hertzl had devoted his life to the cause of creating the first Zionist congress at Basle, Switzerland on 27th August, 1897 (Lenczowski, 1962, p.373).

The idea of creating an independent state for Jews was supported by Lord Rothschild, the head of the Anglo-Jewish community. Hertzl and Rothschild supported each other and their idea was to establish a Jewish colony either in Sinai or in Cyprus, both then occupied by the Britons (Palestine problem in perspective, 1968: p.21). The native population of Cyprus refused and stood against the idea. Then, the British government offered the possibility of Uganda becoming a territory for the Jewish national home. Hertzl accepted the offer. Soon the idea was given up when Jews came to know that Uganda was a part of an imperialist design as it had an important strategic location (Lenczowski, 1962: p.373).

Zionism as a national movement evoked opposition from Jews themselves. As a result of this movement, immigration began to flow into Palestine that roused the antagonism of Arabs, who were the principal occupants of the land. Their opposition was mainly based on economic grounds. Arabs feared that with higher Jewish level of education and industrial capabilities, the Zionists would swamp Arabs and eventually displace them (Hindawii, 1977: pp.10-15).

Britons played a very vital role in establishing a Jewish state in Palestine as they had promised influential American Jews that they would secure Palestine for their oppressed brethren in Europe. The British Government accepted the Zionists' claim and decided to implement their ideas by securing the isolation of Palestine from the Arab World. The British government adopted a new policy towards Palestine in the famous declaration made, which was published in the form of a letter by the British Foreign Secretary, Arthur Balfour, to the Jewish leader Lord Rothschild spelling out British policy on the creation of a Jewish national state in Palestine (Lutsky, 1969: p. 397). Lord Curzon warned that the term "National Home" really meant a 'Jewish State' in which Arabs would be second-class-citizens (Nadave, 1969: p.18).

With the outbreak of the World War II, the Zionists got benefit of the worldwide sympathy shown to Jews suffering from the Nazi persecution by Hitler in Germany and Eastern Europe (Nahal, 1981). During this period, they braced themselves to meet the challenges facing them. They organized the Zionist military organization, Haganah, in a big way (Berindranath, 1969, pp.30-31). Arabs, were helpless since most of the Arab countries had either become a theatre of war or were under actual imperialist domination. Moreover the Zionists started wooing American public opinion. So as to influence the American government, on May 11, 1942, the Congress of World Zionism, held in New York, decided to make Palestine a Jewish Commonwealth and expel its Arab population. In February, 1944, the American Congress declared that the doors of Palestine would be open for free entry of Jews who had been victims of Nazi persecution. There would be full opportunity for colonization so that the Jewish people could finally call Palestine a free and democratic Jewish Commonwealth (Nadave, 1963, p.25).

By the end of the war, Arabs found themselves facing a powerful front composed of Britain, America and the Zionists, all of them aiming at transforming Palestine into a Jewish State, thus establishing a dangerous and unstable situation in the heart of the Arab World as well as in the West Asia region (Kayyali, 1970). The first step in this direction was taken by the Anglo-American Commission which studied the matter and finally recommended that Palestine should be open to Jewish immigrants unconditionally and that 100,000 Jews should be admitted at once into Palestine (Khouly, 1973).

On April 2, 1947, the Palestine problem was referred by Britain to the General Assembly of the United Nations Organization. A special committee was set up who visited Palestine and presented a report to the regular full session of the General Assembly. There were two majority and minority reports. The majority voted to cut up Palestine into three parts: an Arab state, a Jewish state and the city-state of Jerusalem under an international regime. The minority voted for the creation of a federated state of Palestine composed of Jews and Arabseach enjoying local autonomy. The plan for partition was carried by a majority with Britain abstaining from voting and the Soviet Union favouring the partition (Lutsky, 1969, pp. 397-398).

The General Assembly appointed a commission to put the resolution into effect and called upon the Security Council to assist it in the implementation of the plan. But Britain had already decided to withdraw on May 14, 1948. The only powers left to execute the United Nations plan for partition were the United States and the Soviet Union. But the two superpowers were distrusted of each other and the matter was left to Arabs and Zionists who now prepared for the final struggle. Arabs were consistently against the policy of partition and they opposed all the resolutions which called for the division of Palestine, and put forward some alternatives which were good and just. They agreed to the establishment of a United Federal State of Palestine in which the Jewish population could enjoy full rights and protection. Alternatively, they offered to get the matter settled through a plebiscite in Palestine; and, as a final resort, they wanted to test the resolution on partition in the World Court (Sherwood & Hopkins, 1948, pp. 871-2).

Haganawas one of the most notorious Jewish terrorist groups besides the Argon and Stern Gangs that destroyed Arab properties. One of the most disastrous of such acts was a massive attack, launched without any mercy, on the Arab village, DeirYassin, where a small Arab community lived surrounded by Jewish settlements in the Jerusalem district. Most of the Arab inhabitants in the said village, including children, women and oldies were massacred and their houses destroyed. The surviving ones took shelter in neighboring Arab states as refugees (Morris, 1948, pp. 83-4, 134).

On May 15, 1948, the Jewish National Council meeting at Tel Aviv proclaimed the Jewish state of Israel (Frazer, 1995, p.45). By that time the Zionists had already occupied most of the towns and had seized lands which were not included even in the notoriously unjust partition resolution. On its part, the United States extended its recognition to Israel within a few hours. But Israel found itself at war with its Arab neighbors as soon as it was born.

5. The legitimacy of Israel according to the partition resolution, and the invalidity of the legal foundations upon which it was founded, and the recognition:

5.1. The legitimacy of Israel according to the partition resolution:

As it is known to all; Israel gained the legitimacy of its foundation on the basis of Resolution No. (181) of the United Nations, known as the Partition Resolution. Although the decision was not fair and just, and despite the majority of the Palestinians, the United Nations decided with its majority members, to divide Palestine against the wishes of its original inhabitants. It decided to allocate about 55% of Palestine for the Jews, who until then owned only 7% of Palestine (Khattab, 2018). The decision adopted the partition plan for Palestine to end the British Mandate over Palestine and divide its lands into three new entities: Arab state, Jewish state and the Corpus Separatum of Jerusalem (Yale University Press, 2008: p. 47). The content of the resolution emphasized that the Arab state would be established with full sovereignty ten years after the establishment of the Jewish state?!

The vote on the resolution was on November 29, 1947, when the members of the United Nations were only fifty seven. The fifty six countries participated in the vote, all member States except Thailand. Thirty-three votes were in favor of partition, thirteen voted against it, ten countries abstained from voting, and one country was absent. When the result of the vote was announced, the Arab delegates withdrew from the meeting and announced in a collective statement their rejection of the plan and their denunciation of it. Commenting on this subject, then-US Secretary of Defense James Forrestal said in his memoirs: "The methods used to pressure and coerce other nations within the framework of the United Nations were scandalous" (fkhattab, 2018).

The reactions to the partition decision come from the standpoint of international laws, the laws of occupation and the laws of the United Nations. The decision to divide Palestine had opposition that continues to this day, because Palestine is an Arab country that was under the British Mandate since 1922 until 1948, and after the end of the British Mandate decided handed over to the Zionists. According to the universal laws of occupation (the Geneva Conventions), protected persons themselves may not waive their rights (Article 8 of the Fourth Convention) and agreements concluded between the occupying power and local authorities cannot deprive the population of the occupied territory from the protection provided by international humanitarian law (Article 47

of the Fourth Geneva Convention). According to internationally accepted laws and legislation, after the end of the Mandate, the country must be handed over to its true owners (Nahal, 1981).

The decision of the United Nations was very welcome among the Jews because it allowed the establishment of Israel on the ruins of the homeland of the Palestinians, which they have long dreamed of, was the first step to realize their dream of establishing a Greater Israel from the Euphrates to the Nile. Being an imperialist colonial project in the region with the support of the West. Since its establishment, Israel has worked to Judaize Palestine, and issued a set of laws related to immigration, citizenship and land seizure, including the Absentee Property Law, the Emergency Law, the Nationality Law and other policies that would enable it to seize all of the historic land of Palestine. The Jewish presence in Palestine was characterized by several characteristics, including: it is the current colonialism; Colonialism in its general sense always seeks to invest the wealth of the colonial countries and enslave their inhabitants, but the Jewish presence in Palestine was not satisfied with exploiting the land, but rather sought to expropriate it completely, and to eradicate the original society to replace it with a Jewish community.

The goal of the Jewish presence in Palestine was to build an independent state. It was not like the French or British colonialism, but it continued to seek, plan and look beyond Palestine. As such the Israeli entity tried to justify its legitimacy on the basis of ideological foundations and a religious claim, and that the existence of the state does not depend on military conquest, but on the Jews' belief that they constitute the nationalism of "God's chosen people" and that they returned to their country to establish their state that embraces all the Jews of the world. In addition to that, the Jewish presence was an expansionist settlement, that was not satisfied with the controlled areas and did not recognize the borders that it established, but rather sought and seeks to expand its borders as the opportunity allowed it, by relying on its military power, and this is what happened since 1948 till the present day, where Israel controls and occupies more than 91% of the land of historical Palestine including Jerusalem. The question that arises is what is the shape of the two-state solution that the international community and the United Nations are talking about today?

5.2. *Invalidity of the grounds to which Israel claims its existence:*

In its establishment, Israel relied on a set of legal foundations included in the "Declaration of Independence" on May 15, 1948, through which the Jewish movement was able to present Israel to the whole world. In this section, the study discusses the legitimacy of the foundations for the existence of Israel, and attempts to refute Israel's claims through three elements: the historical right, basic evidence and international covenants, the contradiction of the establishment of Israel with the right of the Palestinian people to self-determination.

5.2.1. *The Historical Right:*

Israel claims that it has a historical and religious right in Palestine, and this can be refuted by: It should be noted here that the name (Israel) goes back to the Prophet Jacob bin Ishaq bin Ibrahim. An explanation that the Children of Israel are not the first inhabitants of Palestine, for the Canaanite Arabs inhabited it for centuries before the advent of Jews. When Jews came to Palestine, they were a minority even at the height of their kingdoms, David and Solomon. The Arab presence and Islam remained in Palestine continuously for 15 centuries. This confirms that Arabs were the owners of the historical right in Palestine and not others. Beside that; Rejection of the Jews' claim that they are national and that the Israelis today are the descendants of the Hebrews and the ancient Jews (Hussein, 1968). Jews are a social, religious sect of different races from different eras. It is difficult to describe them as a nation. Anthropologies and anthropology studies confirm the impossibility of their belonging to one race, and thus the Zionists claim that Jewish immigrants cannot be accepted as they have returned to the land of their grandfathers. Beside that; the absence of a Jewish civilization of their own, and there are no traces of their civilization, for Jews throughout time have been affiliated with one of the great powers, so their civilization is borrowed from Arab civilizations and neighboring countries.

5.2.2. *Basic Evidence and International Covenants:*

Israel claims that its existence is based on a set of international covenants and resolutions, such as: the Balfour Declaration, Mandate Deed and Partition Resolution. All of these covenants can be refuted and responded to: the Balfour Declaration was issued by the British government, which does not have the right to make the promise, as it does not own Palestine, as Balfour's promise and the Mandate Deed contradict Britain's obligations to recognize the independence of the Arab countries in its correspondence with Sharif Hussein bin Ali, and Israel has bypassed the partition decision on the right of land and human.

5.2.3. *The Contradiction of the Establishment of the State of Israel with the Right of the Palestinian People to Self-determination:*

Where it imposed on the Palestinian Arab people displacement and transformation into refugees with the loss of their lands, homes and properties, expelled from them and denied return to them, and at the same time gave the right to all Jews of the world to come and settle in Palestine (Sayed, 1975).

5.3. *Recognition of Israel and Jews' Original Homeland:*

5.3.1. *Recognition of Israel:*

After Ben-Gurion announced the establishment of Israel as an independent, sovereign state, recognized by the Soviets and America, respectively. Truman was quick in five minutes after that announcement to recognize it

real (Defacto). Three days after, Stalin went further than Truman did, as the Soviets recognized Israel legal (Dejure). According to the theory of recognition in international law, the difference between Defacto and Dejure recognition is that the Defacto recognition is a temporary recognition while the Dejure recognition is a final recognition, means that the first who recognized Israel was the Soviets, and this is a conclusive evidence that the Soviets also wanted to get rid of the Jews and keep them away from the Jewish District of Birobidzhan (Ghunaimi, 1976).

5.3.2. Jews' Original Homeland:

Of course, not all information and facts are known to everyone. There is information that even many historians, politicians, researchers and scholars do not know; this is certainly intended for the purpose of obliterating minds, falsifying facts, concealing information and obscuring them. For hundreds of years, there have been fabricated crises in various regions of this world, run by the board of directors of the hidden world, or what is known as global Zionism. Among those information and facts that have been obscured is the existence of an authentic homeland for Jews in the world since 1928, but global Zionism attempted as to persuade Jews and tempt them to leave their original homeland and immigrate to Palestine. All studies, investigations, historical and archaeological evidence, both material and moral, indicate that Palestine is an Arab land and that the Zionist entity (Israel) has another homeland and it still present in southeastern Russia. The original homeland of Jews is the Jewish Republic of Birobidzhan (bbc.com, 2019).

All the historical literature that discusses the origin of the search for a national home for the Jews states that Jews stood in front of multiple options to establish their state, some of those options were suggested by great countries, and others were intellectuals and politicians. The first serious step in the Zionist project began after the establishment of the Jewish Students Association in the Ukrainian city of Kharkov, the Belo Association in 1882, and this is another indication that the beginnings of thinking about establishing a Jewish homeland started from the lands of the Soviets. Where it was decided by the Zionist movement and the imperialist countries to establish the homeland for Jews, either in Argentina, Sinai, Uganda, Libya, Madagascar, or on the Grand Island in the Niagara River. But in the end the choice fell on Palestine. This is what the Zionist movement and its collaborators from the imperialist countries were planning. The question that arises is; will the Zionist movement and its imperialist states agree that the Jewish state is established in any place other than Palestine? The answer is no, because this absolutely does not serve their scheme, that aims at controlling the region for years to come.

Most of the details are known to anyone who reads the history of the establishment of Israel, with its events, factors and studying its options, but there are actual historical facts that have been obscured from the general public, and even the category of readers, researchers and others, because it may constitute a strong historical argument supporting the position of Israel. The vast majority in this world does not know that the first Jewish republic is Birobidzhan, or even knows its existence. This republic is the first homeland for Jews in the world, and their migration to it was until the emergence of Zionism and the idea of settling Jews in Palestine. The Zionists succeeded in keeping the media away from the first Jewish republic, which was established without occupying the lands of the original inhabitants, and whose entire population is Jewish. What Israel and the colonial countries supporting it fear is promoting the idea of the return of Jews to their first homeland in this republic and convincing the world of the safe return of Jews residing in Palestine to the Birobidzhan Republic to live in safety and peace, enjoying the atmosphere of the prevailing Jewish culture in it and speaking the language of "Yedish", the language of European Jews without anti-Semitism as it is currently promoted by global Zionism. The Autonomous Republic of Birobidzhan in the Russian Federation, with an area of 41,277 square kilometers, is able to comfortably accommodate and settle all Jews of the world, including Jews of Palestine. Thus, the tragedy of Jews ends first, and the tragedy of the Palestinian refugees ends with their return to their original country, Palestine. But certainly, this proposal and solution contradict the goals of global Zionism and the Western countries that benefit from the existence of Israel in the region. The thing that everyone is ignorant of it that the Jewish Republic was established in 1928 with the support and encouragement of American Jews themselves, led by the Jewish physicist Einstein and the well-known American writer Goldberg.

Thus, global Zionism deceived the whole world when they claimed during the World War II that they desperately needed the land of Palestine as a national home for them, and that they were displaced on the land and that there was no national homeland for them to shelter them. This is what the Zionist movement was keen on when it deliberately used the Basel Conference in its main decision to use the term "homeland" for diplomatic and political reasons, while the real intention of the Basel Conference and Zionism since the beginning was a "Jewish state."

During the disintegration of the Soviets, the Jewish Republic was qualified to declare independence from the Russian Federation, like Chechnya, but Zionism prevented this from happening due to the sensitivity of the emergence of a republic for Jews in a place other than Palestine, in addition to the danger of raising awareness among Jews of the world of the existence of that state and diverting their immigration to it instead from

Palestine. That is why no one has ever heard or knows anything and does not talk about the existence of an alternative homeland for Jews and Israelis other than Palestine.

As the study indicated above, the Republic of Birobidzhan is the capital of the Jewish Autonomous Region in Russia and is considered one of its largest cities. The Jewish Republic also has its own flag and emblem since 1915. What is significant of this study is, that everyone should know this deserted Jewish republic, considered the first land of Jews from all over the world collected in 1928 twenty years before the declaration of Israel. To shed more light on this Jewish republic and learn a lot about it; In the twenties of the twentieth century, Stalin decided to give Jews a homeland in the far east of Russia, so he formally established for them the province of "Iverskia Oblast", that means in the Russian the "Jewish province" that is self-governing, with its capital (Birobidzhan), located five thousand kilometers east of Moscow, and is a sparsely populated area. This Jewish province still exists until present. At that time, Stalin sent his envoys to the United States, Europe and Palestine, carrying to Jews and the governments of the countries in which Jews lived, a clear and specific message that Stalin, for the first time in history, recognized the special status of Jews. He decided to give them an autonomous republic in which they would build their own entity and independent personality at all its educational, cultural, religious, social, political and economic aspects. What made the letter of the Stalin envoys more serious and convincing was that they were carrying pictures showing Birobidzhan Jews working on top of agricultural machinery in their fields, and also showing the smiles of their children playing and studying at schools bearing Hebrew names. On top of all this, Stalin also pledged to give every Jew on his arrival in Birobidzhan to settle and live there (600) Russian rubles; of course this amount was large by the standards of that time, in order to help Jews build their new life in their own self-republic.

Indeed, Jews from all over the world came to live there, from Argentina and Venezuela, and San Francisco, in search of a better life. The Historian David Wazirman mentioned in his book (How It Was), "More than 41,000 Jewish families arrived in Birobidzhan between 1928 and 1938, and settled there", again it is a large number by the standards of that time. But soon the exodus of Jews from Birobidzhan began. The reason is that a Jewish-Zionist party called the Sokonut Foundation, a branch of the Jewish Agency, worked to provide generous support and assistance to Jews to encourage them to immigrate to Palestine and by plane as well. According to the Zionist movement, the project (Birobidzhan) was an experiment and an initial station for their independent state, which is Palestine, and there is no alternative to it. This position was expressed by the head of the Zionist Organization at the time (Chaim Weizmann), who said: "We congratulate and applaud this project, as it is not a substitute for thinking about the establishment of a national home for Jews in Palestine, but rather as a first experience for the idea of a Jewish national home." Stalin's idea lay in granting Jews a state in Birobidzhan, first to keep them away from decision-making centers in the Soviet state, and secondly to group them in an area that would be easy to follow and use in the future.

Through the foregoing, the question arises: Who created Israel, then? More than a hundred years ago, specifically in 1917, Arthur Balfour, the British Foreign Secretary, wrote a letter to Baron Rothschild, one of the British Jewish leaders, in which he informed him that the government of his country supported the establishment of a Jewish homeland in Palestine. About six decades later, specifically in the middle of 1973, John Biden, the current US president, stood in the Senate, after returning from a visit to Israel, saying that "if Israel did not exist, the United States of America would have to find it" (Saban, 2020).

More than three decades later, the famous Russian Jewish writer Leonid Mlechin published a book in Moscow in 2005, entitled "Why did Stalin Created Israel," in which Mlechin said, "Israel would not have come into existence, if Stalin had not wanted it." According to the author the Jewish state was created not by the USA, but by the Soviet Union. This state would not have survived if Stalin, the best friend of Zionists at that time, had not provided it with arms and soldiers against the will of many countries, including the USA. Why did Stalin create Israel, and why did he change his mind so quickly and realign with the Arabic countries? (Mlechin, 2005).

So, who contributed more to the establishment of Israel? Recently, the Egyptian writer Sami Emara, an expert in Russian affairs, published a book seeks to answer this question. The importance of the book is due to its being the first Arabic publication documenting an unprecedented number of documents, and for two important periods in the history of the modern Middle East region. The first period relates to the establishment of Israel, while the second period relates to Arab-Soviet relations. The Egyptian writer says that the objective of the book is to "reconsider common ideas regarding the importance of the Balfour Declaration in the establishment of Israel". The writer, who has lived and worked in Moscow as a press correspondent for more than 50 years, relies on documents of the Russian Foreign Ministry, and testimonies of prominent Soviet personalities, in documenting the role of the Soviet Union in the establishment and support of Israel. And those official documents reveal that "the effort and assistance provided by the Soviet Union was the main factor in establishing the feet of Israel, in contrast to the common belief that the British promise issued in November 1917, known as the Balfour Declaration, was the most important factor in establishing the state." The writer documents the testimonies of influential Russian figures, such as Mikhail Poltoranin, the first Minister of information for former Russian President Boris Yeltsin, regarding Stalin's personal role in the establishment of Israel (Emara, 2021).

In confirmation of what was mentioned above, in recent years, the English woman, Michelle Renov, a political activist, laid out her plan to solve the Arab-Palestinian-Israeli conflict, represented by the return of Jews to the Jewish Republic "Birobidzhan". Historians consider that the period of the thirties witnessed two national homelands for Jews, where Jews were divided between two calls for a national homeland and a promised land, one in Palestine and adopting Zionism as a call to it, and the second in Birobidzhan adopting Soviet communism, contributing to its establishment with great enthusiasm. Here, the English lady Michelle Renov asserts that the republic was established with the support and encouragement of American Jews themselves, represented by a body whose membership included the Jewish scholar Einstein and the well-known American Jewish writer Goldberg, as mentioned earlier in this study as well (youtube,2009).

From the point of view of the plan of the English woman, Michelle Renov, the matter can be applied logically in its presentation, due to the availability of several factors, the first of which is the prevailing Jewish culture in Birobidzhan, and the second is that its area, which is equivalent to the size of Switzerland, allows this just solution and an end to the tragedy of the Palestinians, where the population density is 14 people per square mile compared to 945 square miles in Israel and 1,728 square miles in the Palestinian territories. For this purpose, an organization has been established that vigorously promotes this solution, bearing the name of the Republic of the Jews, and Ms. Renov does not let the opportunity pass without trying to spread the idea that is being blackout by the media. For this, she accused by the Israeli media of being a Holocaust denier and an anti-Semite (Emara, 2021).

The Jews today refuse to talk about this matter, considering that it took place during the "anti-Semitic" era of Stalin, but the researcher rejects these allegations and asserts that Stalin tended to give each of the ethnicities of the Soviet Union a republic of its own, and not only Jews, which denies the accusations of anti-Semitism. The Jewish Republic also constituted a safe haven for Jews who were not welcomed by Russian citizens, as well as Jews from outside the Soviet Union who immigrated to it and found security and peace there. It would have been possible to continue immigration to it had it not been for Zionism and the idea of appropriating the lands of the Palestinian population. Therefore, the 194 member states of the United Nations can choose and support this solution without fear of any accusations of anti-Semitism, because the residents of the Jewish Republic actually live in safety and security.

Ms. Renov considers that Jews lied when they claimed during the World War II that they desperately needed the land of Palestine as their homeland, as there was no need to displace the Palestinians and seize their lands. The option to move to that republic was available to them, but they preferred Palestine because they coveted control over Jerusalem and the Holy lands and beyond (bbc.com,2019). While Ms. Renov deplors the tight media blackout on the reality of the first homeland of Jews, and insisting on referring to it as a province, knowing that the province they claim is equal in size to the size of Switzerland. It resides with the exception of Birobidzhan, which was causing sensitivity to Israel and raising its concerns about the possibility of raising global public awareness of its existence as the first homeland for Jews." Ms. Renov concludes, "Many know nothing of this truth, and the few who have the opportunity to listen to me and know the truth do not easily believe me, but I am ready to dedicate the rest of my life to the world believing me and seeking to resolve the conflict on the basis of this truth."

So, what the researcher concludes, according to the above reveals, is that the former Soviet Union is the first country in the world to establish and support the establishment of Israel, and how could the Soviets not be the first to recognize the establishment of Israel after its proclamation, through legal recognition as mentioned before in this study, according to the international law theory of recognition.

Conclusion

The study of the modern history of the region reveals the great importance that the problem of the region began more than a century; and still is the focus of attention and interest of the colonial countries due to the strategic importance of the region. As a result of the growing awareness of the peoples of the region and the adoption of the ideology of resistance and the expulsion of the colonizer; this was an alarm bell for the colonial states. The colonial states realized that if the peoples of the region united and became one force, then they would expel the colonial states and deprive them of rich resources of the region. That's why was the focus of colonial states together with the Zionist movement saw that the right and shortest way to capture the region by anyhow to remain in the region for centuries to come; Colonial countries began to think of a colonial entity working for them by proxy. The choice fell on Jews of the world and encouraged them to immigrate to the region, specifically in Palestine. Someone may ask why Palestine, because Palestine was at the beginning of the last century one of the most civilized countries in the region. Of course, it is somewhat close to the life of Jews in Europe, which the Jews will adapt to without trouble. In addition to that, Palestine is in the middle of the Arab world; once seized, the colonial states will inevitably be able to divide the Arab world into two parts, a western and an eastern part, and it will be the first nucleus at the beginning of the destruction and fragmentation of the Arab nation.

The study was able to answer the questions as well as to test the hypothesis, and the results of the study were identical to the hypothesis as the researcher assumed as well. The consensus in thought and interest between the Zionist movement and the colonial countries, has contributed to the process of accelerating the immigration of Jews to the region; The Zionist movement aims at controlling the entire world, while the colonial states aim at controlling the region; With continuous, intelligent, and systematic support, the Zionist movement and the colonial states were able to create Israel.

Since the establishment of the State of Israel until today; the region remained in constant conflict and tension, and this is what the colonial states and the Zionist movement planned and succeeded in doing, and the region will remain so for decades to come in constant tension due to the continuity of imperialist colonialism on the one hand and the Zionist movement on the other hand for decades to come as long as Israel is present in the region. The Zionist movement and the colonial states absolutely do not want a solution to the problem of the region, and it is not even possible to allow the establishment of an independent Palestinian state, because this is not in the interest of the imperialist Zionist colonial project. Talking about the two-state solution is a fantasy, and the solution is either one state for the Jews and the Palestinians living side by side in safety and security like any country of the world, or the Jews are returned to their original homeland in Birobidzhan. According to the researcher's opinion, this is the most appropriate solution to resolve the conflict that has been going on in the region for more than a century, if the involved parties in the conflict, really seek and want to find an appropriate solution.

6. Results and Recommendations:

6.1. The Results:

Among the findings of the study, based on what was reviewed in terms of tracking, analysis and evaluation are summarized as follows:

- The region has been living for more than century in an agreed-upon conspiracy between the colonial states and the Zionist movement, carefully planned, and each of them has its own goal. The Zionist movement wants to control the world and the colonial countries want to control the region.
- The Zionist movement agreed with the colonial countries by striking the Arabs and the Jews against each other, on the grounds that they belong to the same race (the children of Abraham). If the Arabs and the Jews converged, they would make the impossible. Therefore, the colonial countries and the Zionist movement found it necessary to drive the wedge of hatred and war between Arabs and the Jews and work on its continuity. Of course, Arabs and the Jews live in the same tragedy.
- The Israeli entity was planted in the middle of the Arab world, aiming at weakening and fragmenting the Arab nation and spreading the policy of suspicion and hatred among the peoples of the nation.
- The Israeli entity in the region works for the benefit of the Zionist movement and the colonial states as a functional state whose goal is to remain superior to the countries of the region by providing them with all means of superiority over others and allowing them to do whatever they want, violating legitimacy and international law at the expense of the countries and peoples of the region.
- The absolute support for Israel comes from the colonial countries and the Zionist movement, because the original homeland of the Jews is not Palestine, but rather the Birobidzhan region in the former Soviet Union, which was established in the year 1928, and the aim was to gather the Jews of the world in that region away from the peoples of Europe who were suffering from the behavior of the multiple Jews at that time.
- The Zionist movement and the colonial countries persuaded the Jews to immigrate to Palestine to live there. Where the Zionist movement derived its name from Mount Zion, one of the mountains of the city of Jerusalem, in order to firstly convince the Jews that through immigration to Palestine they will return to their homeland, and secondly, to justify immigration to Palestine in front of world public opinion; In its early days, the Zionist movement adopted the concept of searching for a homeland and not searching for a state, also to win the sympathy of the peoples of the world, knowing that the Zionist movement, according to its plan, in cooperation with the colonial countries, was looking for the establishment of a state for Jews and not for a homeland as it claimed, but It is worth noting that the Basel Conference, the First Zionist Congress 1897, deliberately used in its main resolution the expression "home" for diplomatic and political reasons, while the real intent of the conference from the beginning was a "Jewish state", and the evidence for that is the establishment of the state of Israel today on more than 90% of Palestine historical land until now.

6.2. Discussions of the Results and Recommendations:

Based on the above results, the study discussed the results and recommends the following:

- The countries of the region should be fully aware that there is no difference between the colonial states and the Zionist movement, for they both are the same; therefore, it is necessary to reconsider the relationship with these countries, put an end to their policies and behavior by not interfering in the internal affairs of the region.

- Arabs and Jews should be fully aware that their problem is caused by the colonial states and the Zionist movement who exploit the Jewish religion to implement its agenda at the expense of Jews of the world. This is a dream impossible to achieve.
- The people of the Arab nation must confront the policies of some Arab political regimes that unconsciously rush towards rapprochement and normalization with Israel, and they must read history well to know the dangers of the Zionist movement. The Arab people should be well aware that the reality of the situation today among the sons of the one Arab people is definitely caused by the Zionist movement, and instead of the policy of normalization, they should call for the revival of Arab unity, which has long been suffering, in this region, from the policy of spreading the seeds of hatred created by the imperialist colonial states to prevent the achievement of unity necessarily.
- The countries of the region should demand the imperialist colonial countries to respect legitimacy and international law by stopping their absolute support of Israel at the expense of the region and the future of its people. Israel has become an illegitimate and illegal state that adopts the policy of apartheid by all standards.
- Researchers, scholars, politicians, and the Arab media should shed light in their studies, speeches and media on the original homeland of the Jews in (Birobidzhan) intensively and continuously.
- The political discourse in regard with the two-state solution must be modified by referring to Partition Resolution No. 181 of November 29 1947, as a basis for the solution instead of the June 4, 1967 lines.
- Thus, the researcher believes, through this study, that the current critical situation in the region will not last forever, and that the Zionist imperialist colonial support for Israel will not last forever, and that the people of the region will not remain silent forever too. The most appropriate and safest solution is the just, comprehensive and lasting solution, the two-state solution, an Arab state and a Jewish state based on the resolution of partition. Otherwise, any solution, if not impossible, will be temporary at the most. And the researcher believes that in event of adoption of all or some of these recommendations, the region will inevitably be free from lasting conflict, even the security and stability will spread all over the region and the world alike.

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Saban, Haim (2020), previously said, "If we had not created it." For these reasons, Biden will rebuild America and strengthen Israel's security. SabanHaim is an Israeli-American benefactor and entrepreneur and founder of the SPAN Center for Middle East Policy at the Brookings Institution.
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